

Fig. 2. Differential counts of bloods taken from three groups of mice, six in each.
 Group 1: Normal healthy mice (■).
 Group 2: Mice inoculated with 1.9×10^6 E.A.C. cells and treated with *Diospyros montana* bark extract (□).
 Group 3: Control mice inoculated with 1.8×10^6 E.A.C. cells (▨).
 Vertical bars represent S.E.M.

Results and Discussion

For the mice in A-group there was practically no significant change in weight of the mice even after twenty days. So the result related to A-group has not been incorporated in Fig. 1. Out of six mice in A-group, one died on 45th day and the others were all alive even after sixty days. While the number of mice survived in E-group after thirty days was four out of six, none of the mice in the C-group survived upto thirty days. From Fig. 1 it is evident that on treatment with C. P., a remarkable regression in the growth of E.A.C. in E-group over the C-group is observed throughout the experiment. From Students' t-test it is found that the difference between E-group and C-group becomes significant from the eighth day after transplantation. It is observed that the mean life span of the E-group is 41 ± 3 , while that of C-group is 26 ± 2 . This indicates an increase of life span of almost 60% for the E-group over the C-group. Table 1 indicates that the mean R.B.C. counts of E- and C-groups do not show any significant departure from that of N-group. However, the W.B.C. count of C-group is found to be increased by 120% over that of N-group while there is no significant difference between the W.B.C. counts of E- and N-groups. Differential count of W.B.C. as shown in Fig. 2 gives a vivid picture of the abnormal haematological pattern of tumour-bearing mice. The drastic increase of neutrophil count in C-group as compared to that of N-group, coupled with the enhancement of total W.B.C. count of the former group, indicates acute neutrophilia of the C-group. In contrast, the

lymphocyte and neutrophil counts of E-group do not vary significantly from those of N-group indicating restoration of normal blood picture on treatment with C.P. This corroborates the possibility of the use of *D. montana* bark extract to inhibit the growth of E.A.C. in mice. It will be our next attempt to characterise the active principles in C.P. by carrying out elaborate fractionation followed by extensive bio-assay.

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α -Amyrin Acetate from *Catharanthus rosea* Linn

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CATHARANTHUS rosea Linn (Syn. *Vinca rosea* Linn) has been the subject of numerous investigations for its alkaloidal constituents. The intense interest in the chemistry of the plant is due to the novelty¹ in structural types of alkaloids in the plant and the role of the plant has played in the understanding of the biogenesis² of indole alkaloids.

We were interested to examine the neutral constituents of the plant. The petroleum-ether extract of the air dried powdered stem of *Catharanthus rosea* by column chromatography over silica gel furnished a crystalline compound, $C_{32}H_{52}O_2$, M^+ 468, m.p. 224°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 77^\circ (C_6H_6)$. The ir spectrum showed characteristic band for acetoxy group at 1730 cm^{-1} . The pmr spectrum (90 MHz, $CDCl_3$) showed signals at 5.2 (m, 1H), 4.5 (m, 1H), 2.01 (s, 3H).

The product and its deacetylated product were compared directly with authentic samples showing the triterpene isolated was α -amyrin acetate.

NOTES

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